

MOIN4Herbie deliverable 3 - List of existing ontologies and evaluation for usage within MOIN4Herbie context available

Authors: Linda Baldewein (Hereon), Claas Faber (GEOMAR), Smruthishree Srinivasa (Hereon), Carsten Schirnick (GEOMAR), Helmke Hepach (GEOMAR), Catriona Eschke (Hereon), Fabian Kirchner (Hereon)

Publication date: August 30th, 2024

Figure 1: MOIN4Herbie logo

Introduction

Purpose of this document

This document contains deliverable #3 *List of existing ontologies and evaluation for usage within MOIN4Herbie context available* of the project MOIN4Herbie - Maintenance Ontology and audit log Integration for Herbie funded by the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC). Deliverable #3 is part of work packages 2 *Maintenance metadata requirements specifications and development of generalized protocols* and 3 *Integration of maintenance ontologies in Herbie*. In this document, existing Controlled Vocabularies and Ontologies are evaluated regarding their suitability for the MOIN4Herbie project. This is done as a necessary preparation for deliverable 4 “Customized ontology for maintenance metadata”.

Controlled vocabularies

Controlled vocabularies are collections of terms and the definition of these terms. Vocabularies are generally grouped by specific topics and subtopics within domains. They are used to organize knowledge as alphabetical lists that can be used within ontologies and other semantic structures.

Ontologies

In information science, ontologies are a formalization of concepts, their relations and properties. Using ontologies allows to collect input which is right away fit for purpose as findable, machine-readable and interoperable (meta)data. Ontologies can ensure the usage of controlled vocabularies and organize the knowledge stored within for assessability and thus reuse.

Ontologies within Herbie

The collection and use of sensor data is crucial for scientists monitoring and observing the Earth’s environment. In particular, it enables the evaluation of real natural phenomena over time and is essential for the validation of experiments and numerical simulations. Assessment of data quality beyond statistics includes knowledge and consideration of sensor state, including operation and maintenance, e.g. calibration parameters and maintenance time windows. Today, maintenance metadata is often collected even digitally but not readily accessible due to a lack of standardization and findability. In the HMC project MOIN4Herbie, digital recording of FAIR sensor maintenance metadata is developed using the electronic lab notebook Herbie. Herbie relies on ontologies and vocabularies to generate user-friendly web-forms for collecting, validating and then provisioning FAIR (meta)data.

Approach

Controlled vocabularies

In the project proposal, only a list and evaluation of ontologies was planned. However, controlled vocabularies are commonly used within the sensor community to describe for example sensor types, observed properties and other terms.

We collected a list of controlled vocabularies and checked if they fit into one of the following categories that were deemed relevant within the project:

- Description of devices, sensors and sensor systems
 - Vocables describing a sensor itself, e.g. sensor types, manufacturer, serial number.
 - This category is further subclassed in
 - * Description of Platforms / Things
 - * Description of Sensors
 - * Description of Parameters / Observed Properties
 - * Description of Units of Measurement
 - * Description of data processing
- Actions associated with a device, a sensor or a sensor systems
 - Maintenance activities and other activities
 - * Roles and Groups of Persons
 - Roles that persons can have in the context of device activities, or groups of persons involved in device activities
 - * Operating Environment
 - Vocables describing the physical or organisational environment of device operations
 - * Physical Operating Environment e.g. in the water, in the air, location, access conditions
 - * Organisational Operating Environment e.g. organisational contexts (campaigns, cruises, projects), resources (budgets, time constraints)

Within MOIN4Herbie we plan on reusing the already existing sensor description within the O2A REGISTRY, which will be facilitated by reusing their controlled vocabularies. Thus, we also checked the O2A REGISTRY API for all vocabularies used within.

Rating of controlled vocabularies

- Subjective *specificity* rating for each vocabulary for first estimation of relevant ontology level (top-level vs task|domain|application)
 - ‘-’: very general vocables
 - ‘-’: mostly general vocables
 - ‘o’: some general, some specific vocables
 - ‘+’: mostly specific vocables
 - ‘++’: very specific vocables

- Subjective *applicability rating* for each vocabulary to estimate how relevant vocabulary is for MOIN4herbie
 - ‘-’: no relevant vocables
 - ‘-’: mostly irrelevant vocables
 - ‘o’: some relevant, some irrelevant vocables
 - ‘+’: many relevant vocables
 - ‘++’: almost all vocables relevant
- Check / count how many vocables are included in REGISTRY vocable groups to see the reuse potential

Ontologies

Using different ontology look-up services, e.g. EMBL-EBI Ontology Lookup Service and NFDI4Ing Terminology Service, various ontologies from top-level to domain specific ontologies were identified that have the potential of being reused in the sensor maintenance ontology used in MOIN4Herbie.

Ontologies rating

- Subjective *specificity* rating for each ontology for first estimation of relevant ontology level (top-level vs task|domain|application)
 - ‘-’: very general ontology
 - ‘-’: mostly general ontology
 - ‘o’: some general, some specific ontology
 - ‘+’: mostly specific ontology
 - ‘++’: very specific ontology
- Subjective *applicability rating* for each ontology to estimate how relevant ontology is for MOIN4herbie
 - ‘-’: no relevant ontology
 - ‘-’: mostly irrelevant ontology
 - ‘o’: some relevant, some irrelevant ontology
 - ‘+’: many relevant ontology
 - ‘++’: almost all of ontology relevant

Results

Controlled vocabularies

Name	Source	Specificity	Applicability	Usage in O2A Registry
MIDA Coastal Erosion Thesaurus	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/A04	++	-	DeviceTypes : 1
BODC Standard Operating Procedures and Protocols for environmental observations	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/B11	++	-	OnlineResourceRoles : 1
BODC Platform Models	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/B76/current/	++	-	DeviceTypes : 1
CI OnlineFunctionCode	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/G02	-	-	OnlineResourceRoles : 6
CI RoleCode	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/G04	-	o	ContactRoles: 5
DS InitiativeTypeCode	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/G07	-	++	EventTypes: 1
MD DatatypeCode	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/G12	-	-	SensorOutputTypes: 1
SeaDataNet device categories	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L05	+	++	DeviceType: 93, SensorOutputTypes: 2
SeaVoX Platform Categories	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L06	o	+	DeviceTypes: 16
SeaVoX Device Catalogue	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/L22	++	o	DeviceTypes: 9
MEDIN data format categories	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/M01	-	-	SensorOutputType: 1
NERC Environmental Data Centres DataCite General Resource Types	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/N06	-	-	DeviceTypes: 1
BODC Parameter Usage Vocabulary	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P01	++	-	SensorOutputType: 6, DeviceTypes: 1

Name	Source	Specificity	Applicability	Usage in O2A Registry
SeaDataNet Parameter Discovery Vocabulary	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P02	+	-	SensorOutputType: 6, DeviceTypes: 2
Global Change Master Directory Science Keywords V5	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P04	-	-	SensorOutputType: 4
Climate and Forecast Standard Names	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P07	o	-	SensorOutputType: 9
Global Change Master Directory Instrument Keywords	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P10	+	o	DeviceTypes: 16
Global Change Master Directory Science Keyword variables	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P14	o	-	SensorOutputType: 2, DeviceTypes: 1
Marisaurus Thesaurus	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/P21	++	-	SensorOutputType: 4, DeviceTypes: 4
Argo sensor types	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/R25	++	-	DeviceTypes: 1
BODC parameter semantic model analytical method entity descriptions	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S04	++	+	DeviceTypes: 15
BODC parameter semantic model data processing entity descriptions	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S05	++	-	SensorOutputTypes:1
BODC parameter semantic model parameter entity names	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S06	o	-	SensorOutputTypes: 5
BODC parameter semantic model parameter statistic	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S07	-	-	SensorOutputTypes: 2
BODC parameter semantic model physical entity subgroup names	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S19	++	-	SensorOutputTypes: 2
BODC parameter semantic model chemical substances	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S27	++	-	SensorOutputTypes: 7
SeaDataNet Sensor Web Enablement and SensorML type vocabulary	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/W01	-	+	SensorOutputType: 1, DeviceTypes: 1
SensorML History Event Types	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/W03/current/	+	++	EventTypes:6

Name	Source	Specificity	Applicability	Usage in O2A Registry
BODC dataset roles	https://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/C89/current/	+	+	NA
BODC parameter semantic model component names	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S01/current/	-	o	NA
BODC parameter semantic model sphere names	http://vocab.nerc.ac.uk/collection/S21/current/	o	o	NA
ODM2 Method Type Vocabulary	http://vocabulary.odm2.org/methodtype/	+	+	NA
ODM2 Action Type Vocabulary	http://vocabulary.odm2.org/actiontype/	+	+	NA
ODM2 Annotation Type Vocabulary	http://vocabulary.odm2.org/annotationtype/	o	-	NA
ODM2 Site type	http://vocabulary.odm2.org/sitetype/	++	o	NA
ODM2 Equipment Type Vocabulary	http://vocabulary.odm2.org/equipmenttype/	-	+	NA
ODM2 Relationship types	http://vocabulary.odm2.org/relationshiptype/	-	o	NA
eWorkOrders Maintenance Terms and Definitions Glossary	https://eworkorders.com/maintenance-terms-definitions/	+	-	NA

Table 1: List of controlled vocabularies and evaluation for reuse within the MOIN4Herbie context. See the approach section for details on the rating process.

Ontologies

Shortname	Source	Name	License	Specificity	Applicability
SOSA	http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/	Sensor, Observation, Sample, and Actuator (SOSA) Ontology	W3C Software and Document Notice and License	+	++
SSN	http://www.w3.org/ns/ssn/	Semantic Sensor Network Ontology	W3C Software and Document Notice and License	+	++
OMPD	https://spec.equonto.org/ontology/maintenance-procedure/conditional-maintenance-task-ontology/	Ontology for Maintenance Procedure Documentation (OMPD) Conditional Maintenance Task Ontology	https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT	++	o
OMPD SPO	http://spec.equonto.org/ontology/maintenance-procedure/static-procedure-ontology	https://industryportal.enit.fr/ontologies/OMPD-SPO	https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT	++	o
MNT-ACT	http://spec.equonto.com/ontology/maintenance-work-management/maintenance-activity-ontology	https://industryportal.enit.fr/ontologies/MNT-ACT	https://opensource.org/licenses/MIT	+	o
MRO	https://github.com/iofoundry/ontology/tree/master/maintenance	Maintenance Reference Ontology	http://opensource.org/licenses/MIT	+	++
BFO	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/bfo.owl	Basic Formal Ontology	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/	-	++
IAO	http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/iao.owl	https://terminology.nfdi4ing.de/ts/ontologies/iao	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/	-	o

Shortname	Source	Name	License	Specificity	Applicability
PROV	https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/	PROV-O: The PROV Ontology	W3C Software License	-	++
PPLAN	http://vocab.linkeddata.es/p-plan/index.html	The P-PLAN Ontology	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/	+	o
LIS	https://rds.posccaesar.org/ontology/lis14/ont/core/	Industrial Data Ontology	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/	o	o
time	http://www.w3.org/2006/time	Time Ontology in OWL	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/	++	+
OWL	www.w3.org/2002/07/owl	The OWL 2 Schema vocabulary (OWL 2)	Copyright © 2012 W3C® (MIT, ERCIM, Keio), All Rights Reserved. W3C liability, trademark and document use rules apply.	-	+
IOF-core	https://spec.industrialontologies.org/iof/ontology/core/Metadata/coreModule?version=release%2F202301	IOF Core Ontologies Library	http://opensource.org/licenses/MIT	+	-
IOF -scro	https://spec.industrialontologies.org/iof/ontology/supplychain/SupplyChainReferenceOntology/?version=release%2F202301	Supply Chain Reference Ontology	http://opensource.org/licenses/MIT	+	-
TERN	https://linkeddata.tern.org.au/viewers/tern-ontology	TERN Ontology	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/	o	-
Agent Ontology	https://github.com/CommonCoreOntology/CommonCoreOntologies/blob/develop/src/cco-modules/AgentOntology.ttl	Agent Ontology	BSD 3-Clause	-	o

Table 2: List of controlled ontologies and evaluation for reuse within the MOIN4Herbie context. See the approach section for details on the rating

process.

Discussion and conclusion

Controlled vocabularies

In total 38 different vocabularies were rated with the categories described in the approach section. The authors are aware that more controlled vocabularies exist that may be applicable, but we decided to focus on the most commonly used once within the Earth and Environment sensor data domain as well as the maintenance vocabularies that we found.

Controlled vocabularies with a rating of + or ++ as well as all vocabularies heavily used by the O2A REIGSTRY are planned to be reused within the currently developed sensor maintenance ontology. Currently, a working group including co-author Carsten Schirnick, is working on reducing the number of controlled vocabularies used within REGISTRY to describe sensors. Within MOIN4Herbie, we plan on reusing their results and keep the list of used controlled vocabularies as short as feasible.

Ontologies

In total 17 different ontologies were rated with the categories described in the approach section. The authors are aware that more controlled ontologies exist that may be applicable, however we focused on the domain ontologies most closes related to sensors and sensor maintenance and the top-level ontologies used within the previously identified ontologies.

Several ontologies that looked promising, as they were very relevant on the domain level, turned out to not be reusable, because they lacked proper description of their classes or properties or because the server where the ontology is published is not reachable. After intially looking at a wide range of ontologies, we decided to limit the number of reused ontologies as much as possible to ones that are already reused a lot and thus well adapted.

We initially underestimated the ontology PROV, an ontology to represent and interchange provenance information, because the term provenance is used differently within FAIR data management compared to ontologies. PROV focuses on activities in time that relate to entities and are attributed to some agent. Maintenance processes, when heavily generalized, can be described by exactly such terms.

A special focus during the upcoming ontology development will fall on the ontology SOSA, because its classes align with the terminology within the SensorThings API. Within the HMC project STAMPLATE the metadata fields within the STA are mapped to metadata fields within sensor management systems such as the REGISTRY. We will incorporate the sensor maintenance data at a later stage of the project into the STA endpoint and thus will simplify the process by already aligning the ontology during the development to the STA interface.